

IMPROVING PRAGMATIC SKILLS OF HIGHER EDUCATION (MEDICAL) STUDENTS BASED ON INNOVATIVE AND INTERACTIVE METHODS

Atamurodova Munira Makhamadievna

Teacher of Termez Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

Turaev Diyorbek Alisher o'g'li

Student of Termez Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

Abstract: In this accelerating globe, the most optimal way to increase the effectiveness of general education is to organize lessons using interactive methods. So, what are interactive methods? What didactic possibilities do they have? What results can be guaranteed by the appropriate and purposeful use of interactive methods in the process of mother tongue education? We will try to answer these questions in this article.

Key words: interactive, module system, innovative technology, interactivity, lingo didactics, lingo pedagogy.

The most correct first step in finding answers to the above questions is to get acquainted with the basic concept - the dictionary meaning of the term "interactive". The concept of "interactive" is derived from the English word "interact" (in Russian "interactive"), from the lexical point of view "inter" - mutual, two-way.

Interactive education is education based on the organization of action based on mutual cooperation in order to acquire knowledge, skills, competences and certain moral qualities of its participants. Interactivity is the ability of the participants of the educational process to organize action based on mutual cooperation in order to acquire knowledge, skills, competences and certain moral qualities. From a logical point of view, interactivity, first of all, represents the conduct of conversation (dialogue), actions and activities based on mutual cooperation. It is necessary to thoroughly understand the content of mother tongue education, the organization of teaching forms at the optimal level, and the enrichment of the theory of formation of a well-rounded person with various new ideas. Currently, modern methods of teaching are widely used in the process of mother tongue education. The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process. When choosing educational methods, it is appropriate to choose each native language based on the didactic task of the lesson.

Theoretical issues of studying and applying foreign experience in teaching. The educational process, based on the use of interactive teaching methods, is organized taking into account the knowledge process of all students, without exception. Working together means that everyone makes their own personal contribution, exchanges knowledge, ideas,

and methods of work in the work process. The essence of innovative methods is to organize the educational process in the form of dialogue that helps students express their thoughts, analyze problematic situations and find effective ways to solve them. Such methods help to increase the level of education, develop students, and form skills and abilities that they will use in their future professional activities.

Improving students' knowledge of "Innovative technologies" in the general education system and forming their understanding and practical skills about "Innovative technologies"; formation of students' theoretical knowledge and practical skills related to "Using innovative technologies";

The theoretical issues of teaching students communication skills based on innovative technologies and interactive methods are the formation of theoretical knowledge and practical skills about "designing and implementing the educational process based on innovative technologies". We have studied the state requirements for the content of mother tongue education, scientifically analyzed them, and studied many scientific studies. We have come to the following conclusion. As it is known from lectures and scientific researches, "Innovative technologies" have been considered in a certain sense and many literatures have been created as a result of conducting many scientific researches. Today, as a result of the development of science and technology and innovative technologies, the interest and attention to increase the effectiveness of mother tongue education using innovative pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. In the mother tongue education system, communication skills are used on the basis of modern technologies to find the knowledge acquired by the students themselves, to study and analyze them independently, to evaluate their own knowledge. aimed at correct conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of individuals and teams, as well as for them to freely think and interact with their fellow students. In this process of education, the student becomes a central participant. Many scientists, professors and teachers of higher educational institutions contribute to the problems. During this period, educational manuals such as "Pedagogical Technologies and Pedagogical Skills" (2006) by N.N. Azizkho'jaeva, "Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in Education and Training" (2013) by R. Ishmukhamedov were thoroughly studied and found their importance in finding solutions to our problems. earned The methodology of teaching the subjects "Mother tongue" and "Uzbek language" based on linguodidactics and linguopedagogy is to set the educational goals of students in practical training, to apply advanced pedagogical elements, and to use modern information technologies. it is necessary to improve knowledge, skills and issues related to effective conduct of work and theoretical lessons and practical training.

Ravshan Ishmukhamedov's textbook "Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in Education and Training" reveals the modern problems of pedagogical skills and innovative technologies of school teachers working in the public education system. Modern requirements for the forms and methods of organization of education at the school, as well as students' learning activities, have been thoroughly studied.

The definitions given to the concept of innovative technology are different and they are defined as follows:

- Innovation (English innovation) means introducing something new, renewing, changing something.

Special attention is paid to innovative technologies, scientific-theoretical foundations, developed pedagogical technologies are given. If we apply innovative technologies to the practice of the mother tongue educational content, the exact use is connected with the analysis and pedagogical skills of the teacher. The term "technology" is a Greek word, "techne" - skill, art and "logos" - concept, study. So, technology-craft means art and means the sum of knowledge about methods and means of process implementation, as well as qualitative changes occurring in the object. Innovative pedagogical technologies mean introducing innovations and changes to the educational system, pedagogical process, and teacher and student activities in the mother tongue education system, and the interactive method is mainly used in the implementation of this process. It is a systematic way of identifying, creating and applying all the processes of teaching and knowledge acquisition, taking into account technical means, human potential and their interaction, in order to optimize the forms of education (UNESCO).

The module system is a didactically designed result-oriented unit with meaningful and logical content, consisting of input and output controls. The concept of modular education was introduced by M. Russell in 1971. A module is an interdisciplinary system that incorporates a number of educational subjects belonging to a certain specialty and is a part of a training course with a relatively independent logical end.

The positive side of the module system is its flexibility, creative approach, logical completion and interchangeability. In this system, the acquisition of knowledge leads to the acquisition of knowledge by students in a convenient situation at a high level at low cost and in a short amount of time. A quick-adaptable, easy-to-change, time-saving teaching-methodical system for teachers, the saved time is directed to counseling activities. The educational institution produces talented students with sufficient modern knowledge.

The advantage of the module system is that it can be used as the main educational system or in combination with the existing system at each stage of the educational process.

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